

Tip n' roll

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of the garbage system, Tip N'Roll, ended as our final design in 'Brugerorienteret Design'. The idea is to minimize the amount of garbage on the streets, by increasing the volume of the garbage can. This may sound easy, but with the regulations set by the Factories Inspectorate (Arbejdstilsynet) it's a problem to empty the cans. Our solution is a system with a special designed sack truck. The sack truck has multiple functions; it is the key to remove the garbage can from its base, it transports the garbage can to the garbage van and it still enables the garbage personnel to use the bin-emptying system on their trucks.

THEORY, METHODS AND RESULT

From the SCOT theory, we discovered some problems in Copenhagen. From an analysis of our collected material we realised that the capacity of the bins was not sufficient enough in specific areas.

The great thing about Tip N'Roll is that the garbage man does not have to empty the garbage can 5-6 times a day, but now only 2-3 times, and less garbage will end on the streets due to the three times more space in Tip N'Roll.

Tip N'Roll is a solution that lasts for a long time. With the base in fibre concrete, the garbage can in ABS and the sack truck in steel the system doesn't have a direct impact on the environment. And if someone vandalizes the system, only the garbage can has to be replaced.

The solution is implementable; the system can use the current small garbage trucks because the sack truck is designed to fit.

CONCLUSION

Tip N'Roll is a solution that helps the environment, not only by minimizing the garbage on the streets, but also by minimizing the amount of fuel used on garbage collection. Furthermore it improves the working environment.